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Impact of English Enhancement Program on Nursing Students

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Abstract

This study investigated the effectiveness of the English Enhancement Program (EEP) and its impact on nursing students. The program, offered free of charge for two years to college freshmen, aimed to enhance communication, confidence, and practical application of the English language. A descriptive quantitative research design was employed, with sixty-four (64) nursing students participating. Data were collected through structured questionnaires assessing program effectiveness, implementation, and self-reported improvements in skills and confidence. Findings revealed that the program was very effective and had contributed positively to students. The results indicate that participation in the English Enhancement Program (EEP) contributes to the development of critical English proficiency skills, which are essential for academic success, professional communication, and competitiveness in global healthcare employment. These findings highlight the importance of continuing the program to ensure nursing students are well-prepared for transnational career opportunities. The results of the study may serve as a guide for educational policy planners by optimizing and implementing a more comprehensive English language program to guarantee more secure and competitive global employment credentials for the graduates. To maintain the quality standard of education, the College Department should continue offering the English Enhancement Program to produce nurses who are proficient in communication skills to become globally competitive.

Keywords: English Proficiency; English Enhancement Program; Nursing Students; Career Opportunities; Program Effectiveness

1. Introduction

In today's era of technology and globalization, English proficiency is a valuable talent and skill for professional and academic success, and can surpass multicultural boundaries in today's synergized and unified world. Nurses who are quite articulate in English-speaking skills have a competitive edge in the job market and can relate effectively with colleagues and clients from different cultural backgrounds. By enhancing the English-speaking proficiency of nurses, they can steer the global workforce with confidence and grab opportunities for individual and professional growth.

English is vital for accessing more job opportunities in the future around the globe. For professionals aspiring to expand their career prospects, English proficiency serves as an asset even in business transactions with multinational corporations having English as the prime language. For instance, proficiency in English opened doors to international business collaborations, allowing individuals to communicate effectively with partners from diverse backgrounds. Moreover, English offers a wide range of career possibilities beyond traditional fields like tourism, teaching, engineering, nursing, medicine, and professionals from various sectors have benefitted from English proficiency by working in foreign countries, enhancing their knowledge, and broadening their horizons.

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Language serves as a doorway to global opportunities and professional growth, enabling nurses and doctors to work in foreign countries. Learning English is not just a practical necessity but also a delightful experience. It fosters connections with individuals worldwide and facilitates effective self-expression. In line with this, the English Enhancement Program (EEP) was implemented to provide nursing students with these opportunities. The program aimed to improve exposure to proper English usage, create a language-rich learning environment, and foster personal growth and confidence in communication.

English helps accelerate one's professional career by facilitating effective communication with colleagues and clients. Participation and engagement in dialogue during workshops, events, and conferences, and networking with people globally, can create high-paying and better job offers. Learning English is not just a practical necessity but also a fulfilling experience that fosters connections with individuals worldwide and facilitates effective self-expression (Oxford House, 2023).

The outcomes of the research conducted by Farooqui et al. (2023) underscored beliefs that individuals gifted with proficient English language are in better positions to excel in the globalized workplace, equipping them with enhanced prospects for employment growth and success. No one can undermine the idea that career success also requires factors like skills, experience, and cultural competencies in addition to language proficiency.

Subsequently, the research results of the study conducted by Wang et al. (2023) revealed a statistically significant relationship between English language proficiency and academic performance, and work success. This study has significant implications for enhancing the quality of teaching English effectively to promote the internationalization of higher education.

The importance of enhancing the nursing students' English skills is reinforced by the growing global academic and health workforce landscape, with over 1,057,188 international students studying in the United States in AY 2022–2023 and global enrollments projected to exceed 8 million by 2025, a trend on which many higher education institutions, particularly in healthcare, heavily depend (Statista, 2023). In today's time, many colleges and universities depend greatly on overseas student revenue for their continuing operations, especially in the health workforce.

In summary, proficiency in communicating in English language provided many professionals, particularly nurses, with a competitive edge in the global job market and supports professional growth and career mobility. Similarly, English proficiency is a vital skill for nurses in a globalized and technologically driven world, as it enhances communication, academic performance, and employability. Hence, the present study examined the effectiveness of the EEP and its impact on the student, particularly in improving communication skills, confidence, and career readiness. As global opportunities in healthcare continue to expand, English proficiency remains a key factor in nurses' academic and professional success.

2. Review of Related Literature

The positive effects of English proficiency, as identified by some researchers, include enabling individuals to express themselves clearly, understand others, and engage in meaningful conversations. English proficiency can also pave the way to create and develop a deeper connection and relationship with clients. It can also create professional development opportunities in a wider geographic area. As noted by Vinnikainen (2022), language proficiency is a partial determinant of individual career choices in the business world.

The result of the study by Daqiq, et al. (2024) revealed that the importance of English was associated with increased connectivity due to globalization. The study also concluded that the importance of English for finding jobs and making a career was well established. With this, it can be inferred that English and employment are correlated with each other, and English language proficiency is amongst the top global employment skills from the viewpoint of educated individuals.

In addition, Peltonen and Hu (2025) emphasized that linguacultural competencies, such as knowledge, skills, and attitudes, play an essential role in ensuring effective global communication, with business professionals identifying them as crucial in real-world transnational interactions. This simply underscores how language skills facilitate communication and relationship building in business contexts.

Many studies have highlighted that one's efficiency in utilizing the English language heightens workplace efficiency and overall business strategies. Furthermore, Fahreza (2023) argued that the mastery of the English language is highly regarded as an important asset in the modern workplace, as it serves as an international language, enabling individuals

to communicate more effectively, participate in global discussions, and gain an opportunity to access important global issues.

However, based on the index done by the global education company, the Philippines fell four notches down to 22nd place out of 111 countries in the 2022 edition of the English Proficiency Index (EPI) (Education First, 2023). This raises concerns about the potential economic and workplace implications of declining English skills.

As revealed in the study of Khoiriyah et al. (2025), English proficiency is strongly linked to employee performance, productivity, and access to better job opportunities in globalized labor markets, making it an essential component of workforce competitiveness. Therefore, any student aspiring to become globally competitive in the field of healthcare professions with low proficiency in English can significantly affect academic performance, especially in pursuing allied health courses.

In the globalized academic landscape, English proficiency has become a crucial skill for researchers and teachers, and in any type of profession where English is used as the primary language. Thus, English proficiency in today's complicated world becomes a key asset for traversing the global landscape successfully. As stated by Aimen and Khadim (2024), the ability to communicate effectively in English is not only a doorway to enhanced career opportunities but also facilitates integration into diverse societies.

Recent studies consistently demonstrate the significant role of English language proficiency in academic success and employability. Ruegg et al. (2024) found that language proficiency has a statistically significant effect on undergraduate academic achievement, highlighting its importance in higher education outcomes. Similarly, Grain et al. (2022) reported that most respondents strongly valued English fluency as essential for managing college coursework and participating effectively in research endeavors.

Beyond academic contexts, English proficiency has been shown to influence employment and economic outcomes. A study conducted by Pearson (2024), involving over 5,000 speakers of English as a second or additional language from Japan, Saudi Arabia, Brazil, Italy, and the United States, revealed that higher English proficiency is closely linked to greater earning potential, finding lucrative job prospects, improved job satisfaction, and increased self-confidence. Notably, 80% of respondents believed that English proficiency directly correlates with earning capacity, with some reporting potential salary increases of up to 80%.

Supporting these findings, Lokhande and Shibu (2024) demonstrated that English proficiency plays a crucial role in the job placement success of students enrolled in the Master of Management Studies. Their findings suggest valuable implications for educational institutions in designing curricula and training programs that strengthen language skills, as well as for students seeking to optimize their employability in an increasingly competitive global labor market.

Proficiency in the English language plays a vital role in shaping one's academic competence, communication effectiveness, and career prospects. Studies consistently show that strong English skills enhance professional interaction, workplace performance, and access to better employment opportunities, particularly in healthcare settings that require clear and accurate communication. These findings support the present study's focus on examining the effectiveness of the English Enhancement Program and its impact on nursing students' skills, confidence, and preparedness for global employment.

Objectives of the Study

The present study aimed to explore the answers to the following questions:

- What is the level of effectiveness of the English Enhancement Program?
- How effective is the implementation of the English Enhancement Program?
- What improvements do nursing students identify after participating in the English Enhancement Program?

3. Methodology

This study employed a descriptive quantitative research design to examine the perceived effectiveness of the English Enhancement Program among nursing students. It was conducted in the nursing department of a private school in Baliwag City, Philippines. The participants were one hundred sixty-four (6) freshman students from Academic Year 2024-2026. Data collection was conducted through questionnaires via Google Forms and focus group discussions. To

analyze the data, descriptive statistics, including mean and standard deviation, were used to determine the level of perceived effectiveness of the English Enhancement Program.

4. Results and Discussion

Table 1 Demographic Profile of the Respondents

	Indicators	Frequency	Percentage
Age	17 years of age	2	3.13%
	18 years of age	15	23.44%
	19 years of age	19	29.69%
	20 years of age	9	14.06%
	21 years of age	6	9.38%
	22 years of age	5	7.82%
	23 years of age	1	1.56%
	27 years of age	1	1.56%
	29 years of age	1	1.56%
	31 years of age	1	1.56%
	33 years of age	1	1.56%
	34 years of age	1	1.56%
	38 years of age	1	1.56%
	39 years of age	1	1.56%
	TOTAL	64	100%
Sex	Male	23	35.94%
	Female	41	64.06%
	TOTAL	64	100%
Academic Year	BSN Level 1 AY 2024 - 2025	28	43.75%
	BSN Level 1 AY 2025 - 2026	36	56.25%
	TOTAL	64	100%

Table 1 presents the demographic profile of the 64 nursing students who participated in the study. The respondents' ages ranged from 17 to 39 years old, with the majority of students aged 18 to 20 years (67.19%), indicating that most participants were traditional-aged freshmen. The distribution shows a higher proportion of female students (64.06%) compared to male students (35.94%), reflecting the typical gender composition of nursing programs. Regarding academic year, 28 students (43.75%) were from BSN Level 1 AY 2024–2025, while 36 students (56.25%) were enrolled in BSN Level 1 AY 2025–2026, showing an almost even representation across groups. These demographic characteristics provide context for interpreting the subsequent evaluations of the English Enhancement Program.

Table 2 Level of Effectiveness of the English Enhancement Program

Criteria	Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
Provide students with greater exposure to the correct use of the English language	4.66	0.57	Very Effective
Create a language -rich environment for a wider scope of learning	4.66	0.60	Very Effective
Encourage the practical application of English language skills in academic and social contexts	4.63	0.60	Very Effective
Provide challenging growth opportunities for the optimum development of their potentials	4.63	0.60	Very Effective
OVERALL MEAN	4.65		Very Effective

Table 2 shows the perceived effectiveness of the English Enhancement Program among the nursing students. The students rated all criteria as very effective, with mean scores ranging from 4.63 to 4.66 and standard deviations between 0.57 and 0.60. The overall mean of 4.65 confirms that the program was perceived as very effective in enhancing students' English skills, providing exposure, fostering practical application, and offering growth opportunities.

Table 3 Level of Effectiveness of the Implementation of the English Enhancement Program

Criteria	Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
Content was presented in an organized manner	4.61	0.63	Very Effective
Content was presented clearly and effectively	4.63	0.60	Very Effective
Was responsive to questions/comments	4.61	0.61	Very Effective
Teaching aids/audiovisuals were used effectively	4.64	0.57	Very Effective
The teaching style was effective	4.69	0.56	Very Effective
Content met stated objectives	4.67	0.56	Very Effective
Content presented applied to my practice	4.58	0.64	Very Effective
OVERALL MEAN	4.63		Very Effective

As shown in Table 3, the implementation of the program was also rated very effective, with mean scores ranging from 4.58 to 4.69 and standard deviations between 0.56 and 0.64. Students noted that the program was organized, clear, responsive to questions, and effectively used teaching aids and audiovisual materials. The overall mean of 4.63 indicates that the program was delivered in a manner that maximized learning engagement and accessibility. This suggests that both the content and delivery of the EEP contributed positively to student English skills enhancement experiences.

Table 4 Reported Improvements Among Nursing Students After the English Enhancement Program in terms of Skills Development

Indicators	Frequency	Percentage
I was able to update my speaking skills	37	57.81%
I acquired new and/or advanced skills in speaking	18	28.13%
I have better knowledge to express myself both orally and in written form	5	7.81%
Others	4	6.25%
TOTAL	64	100%

Table 4 shows that students reported improvements primarily in speaking and communication skills. The majority of students indicated that they were able to update their speaking skills (57.81%) and acquire new or advanced skills in speaking (28.13%). A smaller percentage (7.81%) reported improved ability to express themselves both orally and in written form. These results suggest that the program was particularly effective in enhancing students' oral communication abilities, which is consistent with the program's objectives.

Table 5 Reported Improvements Among Nursing Students After the English Enhancement Program in terms of Confidence and Learning Approaches

Indicators	Frequency	Percentage
I gained confidence in speaking the English language	44	68.75%
I learned a new approach to learning language skills	10	15.625%
It helped me to do better in my school activities	10	15.625%
I do not see the impact of this course on my studies	0	0%
TOTAL	64	100%

Table 5 illustrates improvements related to confidence and learning strategies. Most respondents reported gaining confidence in speaking English (68.75%), while others noted that they learned new approaches to language learning (15.63%) and that the program helped them perform better in their school activities (15.63%). Notably, no student indicated a lack of impact (0%), highlighting the program's overall positive reception.

5. Conclusion

In conclusion, the importance of English language skills in career advancement cannot be undervalued. The findings of this study show that the English Enhancement Program was highly effective, with students rating the program's content and implementation as very effective (overall mean scores of 4.65 and 4.63, respectively). Students reported that the program provided greater exposure to the correct use of English, a language-rich environment, opportunities for practical application, and challenging growth opportunities, confirming its effectiveness in developing English competencies.

Mastering English enhances job prospects and enriches one's access to a diverse range of career possibilities. Investing in English language proficiency, whether for professional success or personal enrichment, is a wise decision that can yield numerous benefits in today's interconnected world. English competency is crucial for overseas job placement, being the global business language, opening doors to multinational companies, diverse roles in nursing and medical care, technology, hotel tourism, and education, assuring higher pay, faster promotions, and easier cross-cultural collaboration. Students in the study reported improvements in speaking skills, communication abilities, and confidence. Many indicated they were able to update their speaking skills (57.81%), gain confidence in speaking English (68.75%), and learn new approaches to language learning (15.63%), demonstrating the program's positive impact on self-perceived English proficiency.

Mastery of the English language can motivate professionals to lead meetings, negotiate, write reports, and work with global teams, significantly increasing employability and earning potentials. English serves as the *lingua franca* for international business; it signifies modernity and competence which is essential for interacting with global clients, partners, and colleagues. It unravels opportunities in multinational corporations and various sectors like medicine, nursing, information technology, tourism, and academia, beyond local markets.

Strong communication skills lead to quicker promotions, higher salaries, and leadership roles, even in non-English speaking countries. English-proficient professionals exude confident participation in meetings, presentations, negotiations, and professional writing. It makes individuals more resilient and effective in diverse international work environments, fostering cross-cultural understanding. Many top companies prioritize English speakers for their ability to negotiate with international business demands, making them more competitive candidates.

Recommendations

To improve English performance, nursing students aspiring to become globally competitive professionals should seriously immerse themselves in English multimedia to enhance communication skills. The teachers and school administrators should encourage their students to practice English speaking daily with partners or even shadowing speakers. Building vocabulary can be enhanced by reading various books, news, and articles to understand sentence structure. Writing summaries of articles read, and joining conversation groups for feedback, focusing on consistent practice skills, including reading, writing, listening, and public speaking.

Watch English movies/TV, listen to English music/podcasts, and follow English news to hear natural speech and rhythm. Talk to oneself, read aloud, or find language partners/clubs for real conversations and feedback. Imitate native speakers in videos or podcasts to improve pronunciation and intonation.

Participate in English discussion clubs or workshops for collaborative practice and building self-confidence. Find meaning for new words and phrases, review them regularly, and try to use them in sentences. Write summaries of news articles or videos to practice comprehension and writing. Join writing groups or workshops to get constructive feedback on one's writing.

Consistency in practice, even a few minutes daily, is better than long, infrequent sessions. Utilize language learning apps for vocabulary, grammar, and assessments. Put English labels on objects to reinforce vocabulary. Use assessment tools to set realistic goals and track progress. Be curious and have fun to learn topics in English to stay committed and motivated to excel in speaking English for a brighter job opportunity as fruits of hard labor, consistency, perseverance, and commitment.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed

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